

CUSUM chart method for continuous monitoring of antifouling treatment of tubular heat exchangers in open-loop cooling seawater systems

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Biofouling

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ABSTRACT

A CUSUM chart method is presented as an alternative tool for continuous monitoring of an electromagnetic field-based (EMF) antifouling (AF) treatment of a heat exchanger cooled by seawater. During an initial experimental phase, biofilm growth was allowed in a heat exchanger formed of four tubes until sufficient growth had been established. In two of the tubes, continuous EMF treatment was then applied. The heat transfer resistance and heat duty (heat transfer per unit time) results showed that biofilm adhesion was reduced by the EMF treatment. EMF treatments resulted in a 35% improvement in the heat transfer resistance values. The proposed CUSUM chart method showed that the EMF treatment increased the useful life of the heat exchanger by ~20 days. Thus, CUSUM charts proved to be an efficient tool for continuous monitoring of an AF treatment using data collected online and can also be used to reduce operation and maintenance costs.

Keywords: Biofouling ; biofilm ; CUSUM chart ; electromagnetic fields (EMF) ; heat exchanger ; seawater

Introduction

Heat exchangers are essential equipment in many industrial processes, and they function by transferring heat from one fluid to another through their walls (Singh and Jakhar 2014). Seawater is considered to be an unlimited resource and is therefore widely used as the cooling fluid in these processes (Trueba et al. 2013). However, the use of seawater results in biofouling, which can adversely affect the system (Delrot et al. 2012; García et al. 2016). Biofouling is defined as the adhesion and accumulation of biotic deposits on submerged or wetted surfaces, and the deposits consist of organic components, such as microorganisms, plants, algae, or animals, associated in a self-produced polymer matrix called a biofilm, which can also include inorganic components, such as salts and/or corrosion products (García et al. 2016). Biofouling causes major operational problems in heat exchangers in the power and processing industries. Natural seawater contains both organic and inorganic molecules and bacterioplankton all of which colonize on heat transfer surfaces to form biofilms. The formation of organic and inorganic deposits on surfaces used for heat exchangers has well-known consequences on heat transfer (Nebot et al. 2007; Eguía et al. 2008; Trueba et al. 2015a); resistance. Biofilms on the heat exchanger surfaces cause additional resistance to heat transfer and therefore reduce

the rate of heat exchange (Delrot et al. 2012). This situation degrades the thermal efficiency of the unit, accelerates corrosion, has environmental consequences, impedes production, and increases the system's operational and maintenance costs, generating both energy and economic losses (Wallhäußer et al. 2012). In industrialized countries, the cost of biofouling in heat exchangers has been found to be 0.25% of gross national product. In industrial processes, the added cost due to biofouling can reach \$50,000 per heat exchanger (Gudmundsson et al. 2008). Therefore, monitoring, detecting, and eliminating biofouling growth as soon as possible is critical to ensure that the heat exchanger works under optimal operating conditions.

Over the last decade, several novel biofouling control strategies for industrial water systems have emerged, including both biological methods (Trueba et al. 2007) and physical methods such as ultraviolet light (Liu and Dong 2008; López-Galindo et al. 2010), electromagnetic fields (Amr and Schoenbach 2000), magnetic fields (Gabrielli et al. 2001), ultrasound (Bott 2001), and reverse flow (Eguía et al. 2008). The various advantages of these biofilm control strategies can be leveraged in the selection of an antifouling method, which must depend on the site's particular conditions, including the composition of the biofilm, the environmental impact of the treatment, safety guidelines, and treatment cost.

Electromagnetic field-based (EMF) methods are particularly attractive because they are environmentally friendly. EMF methods function by generating an electrical current in proportion to the flow of that current, thereby increasing the mobility of ions dissolved in the seawater and accelerating the process of ionic calcium nucleation and precipitation into fine particles of calcium carbonate that become suspended in the flow. These particles of calcium carbonate are dragged by the flow and erode the adhered biofilm by the shear effect of the circulating water and particles. Furthermore, calcium carbonate does not precipitate in the biofilm matrix, and instead affects the intermolecular interactions among extracellular polymers, thereby weakening the biofilm matrix and reducing its adhesion capacity (Shahryari and Pakshir 2008; Xiaokai 2008; Lipus et al. 2011). However, previous experimental studies of the EMF control of industrial and domestic systems using freshwater or artificial water did not report conclusive results (Gabrielli et al. 2001; Shahryari and Pakshir 2008; Xiaokai 2008; Lipus et al. 2011).

In heat exchangers, biofilm formation results in reduced mass flow and a decrease in the difference between the inlet and outlet temperatures. Therefore, biofilm growth can be monitored by a cumulative sum control (CUSUM) chart, which is a statistical technique that represents the cumulative sum of deviations in information from all previous samples. According to previous studies (Jonsson et al. 2007; Boullosa-Falces et al. 2019), the CUSUM is very efficient at detecting a small shift in the mean of a process. This method has been used to detect small but persistent shifts in high-rate GPS (Global Positioning System) carrier-phase measurements (Yi et al. 2016), as well as possible defects in the main bearing of a wind turbine. The method was shown to be fast and reliable at estimating wear development as a function of time (Ghane et al. 2016), and has been used to monitor fuel processing variables in a marine diesel engine where it was effective at detecting slow and progressive deviations (Boullosa-Falces et al. 2017). The method has also been used in the petrochemical industry, (Abbas et al. 2018) to enhance the sensitivity of a control scheme for identifying different quantities of components present in different catalysts.

The main objective of this study was to evaluate the CUSUM chart method as a tool for continuous monitoring of EMF treatment in tubular heat exchangers that use seawater as a cooling fluid.

Biofilm growth was allowed in a heat exchanger comprising a set of four tubes. In two of the tubes continuous EMF treatment was applied to minimize the loss of heat duty (heat transfer per unit time) caused by biofilm. The CUSUM chart method was used to continuously monitor the action of EMF treatments and the results were compared with untreated control tubes. The CUSUM charts proved to be an efficient tool for continuous monitoring of EMF treatment and can be used to decrease the system's operational and maintenance costs.

Materials and methods

Experiment setup

A pilot plant (Figure 1) was established to study biofilm adhesion in heat exchangers. The tubular heat exchanger was designed and manufactured according to the specifications of the Tubular Exchanger Manufacturing Association (TEMA). The shell had an external diameter of 240 mm (20 mm thick) and was made of AISI 304 SS grade stainless steel (SS). The tube sheets were made of AISI 304 SS grade SS. The tube bundle contained four independent tubes of

3,163 mm in length (10.2 mm in diameter and 2.5 mm in thickness) and manufactured of AISI 316Ti grade SS ($C \leq 0.080\%$; $Mn \leq 2.0\%$; $p \leq 0.045\%$; $S \leq 0.030\%$; $Si \leq 1\%$; $Cr 16.0\text{--}18.0\%$; $Mo 2.0\text{--}3.0\%$; $Ti 0.7\%$; $Ni 10.0\text{--}14.0\%$; $N \leq 0.1\%$; Fe Balance %) (N6 class surface roughness). The tubes were furnished under the specification A270 with a roughness (R_a) of $0.8 \mu\text{m}$. To reduce energy loss, the heat exchanger shell was covered with 40-mm-thick glass wool insulation ($k = 0.038 \text{ W m}^{-1} \cdot ^\circ\text{C}$) (Agyenim et al. 2009). Cold seawater flowed into the tubes and heated water flowed out of the tubes but remained inside the shell (termed the shell side).

Figure 1. Pilot plant.

Water heating circuit

A fresh water heating system with a flow rate of $17 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$ was established through the shell side using a rotameter-type flow meter. The inlet shell-side temperature was maintained at 36°C using a proportional-integral-derivative automatic control system (OMRON E5CK, Omron Electronics Iberia, Madrid, Spain) that regulated a motorised three-way valve in the primary circuit where water at 80°C coming from the boiler room released its heat to the water in a secondary circuit through a plate heat exchanger (UFX-26H Sedical), widely used to stabilize the heat load entering the primary circuit in the closed loop. From here, the freshwater was directed to the mixing tank in a closed circuit by a circulation pump (Grundfos MG90SA4-24F 1151IP 44CLF, Algete, Spain) at 0.5 bar.

Seawater cooling circuit

The cooling pump extracted seawater from the Santander Bay ($43^\circ28'\text{N}$, $3^\circ48'\text{W}$) at a depth of 3 m by two centrifugal pumps connected in series (ITUR AU-MI 1.5/10, Zarautz, Spain). In order to separate the water from organic substances such as algae or fine particles, the seawater was subjected to macro-filtration and decanting processes. For this purpose, a strainer filter suction (strainer element with 5.0 mm hole size) was installed in the seawater pump. After this, the seawater was pumped to settling tank (1 m^3) where the sand and other heavier particles settled at the bottom and floating particles were drained from the surface. Then, the seawater was transported to a second tank (1 m^3) which included a turbulence chamber, from where the water passed through filters that kept the macroparticles in a desilting chamber, and then the filtered seawater was pumped at 1.9 bar through the circulation pump (Grundfos CHI 4-50 A WG, Algete, Spain) towards the heat exchanger tubes.

The seawater then flowed through the tube bundle of the heat exchanger at $0.29 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$. The measurement equipment was properly adjusted and calibrated before performing the experimentation. Differential pressure transmitters [PTX 2170-1656 (Accuracy: $\pm 0.1\%$), Sensicon Inc., Highland City, FL, USA] and resistance thermometers [Surface Mount RTD 100 Ω DIN Class A (Accuracy: $\pm 0.15^\circ\text{C}$), Sedem. SA., Barcelona, Spain] were assembled between the inlet and outlet of heat exchanger to carry out an *in situ* real time monitoring system for the seawater. The velocity

across the tubes was maintained at $\sim 1 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ inside the tubes, as measured by positive displacement flow meters [Badger Meter M25 PFT-420 (Accuracy: $\pm 0.1 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$), Badger Meter Europe, Neuffen, Germany] which were assembled at the heat exchanger tubes inlet.

EMF equipment

The EMF treatment agitates dissolved ions (calcium and carbonate) in seawater, causing them to collide and crystallise into small particles which are then dragged in the seawater cooling flow (Shahryari and Pakshir 2008; Xiaokai 2008; Lipus et al. 2011). The velocity through the EMF device was adjusted on 0.08 m s^{-1} . The retention time of seawater in the EMF was 10 s. In this study, the EMF equipment (Figure 2) consisted of two coils placed next to each other, placed in series, separated by 100 mm, rolled around a seawater tube (804 mm in length and with a 50-mm inner diameter), located before the entry of seawater into the heat exchanger. The EMF equipment generated an intensity of 15 mT at a frequency of 1 kHz (12 V) and was controlled by a control unit. Thus, the EMF equipment produced a pulse current to create time-varying fields inside the tube that precipitated calcium and carbonate ions.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the EMF unit.

Biofilm formation on heat transfer resistance

The development of the biofilms that adhered to the internal surfaces of the heat exchanger tubes was monitored *via* the heat transfer coefficient of the tubes. The heat transfer resistance ($R_f [\text{m}^2 \text{ K kW}^{-1}]$) was defined as the sum of the resistance to heat transfer due to the convective and conduction mechanisms; it was calculated using Equation (1) (García et al. 2016):

$$R_f = \frac{A_{in}}{\dot{m}_c \rho_c c_p \ln \left(\frac{T_{h,i} - T_{c,o}}{T_{h,o} - T_{c,i}} \right)} \quad (1)$$

where A_{in} is the total surface covered by biofilm deposits in the tube (m^2), \dot{m} is the cooling water mass flow rate (kg s^{-1}), ρ_c is the seawater density ($1,025 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$), c_p is the specific heat at constant pressure ($4.18 \text{ kJ kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$), $T_{h,i}$ is the fresh water inlet temperature (K), $T_{h,o}$ is the fresh water outlet temperature (K), $T_{c,o}$ is the cooling water outlet temperature (K), $T_{c,i}$ is the cooling water inlet temperature (K).

Continuous monitoring of EMF antifouling treatment by CUSUM

The performance of the EMF treatment on the internal surface of the heat exchanger was monitored through CUSUM control charts (Montgomery 2009). One of the advantages of this type of control charts is the ease of development of its algorithms and implementation and plotting through standard software such as MS EXCEL or more technical software such as Labview. This biofilm detection method was previously validated for the detection and monitoring of biofilm in this type of heat exchanger (Boullosa-Falces et al. 2019). The differences (ΔT) between the outlet

temperatures ($T_{c,o}$) and the inlet temperatures ($T_{c,i}$) of all four tubes were monitored. The means, standard deviation (SD), and the maximum and minimum values of each variable are presented in [Table 1](#).

Table 1. Means, standard deviations, and maximum and minimum values (ΔT).

Variables	Unit	Min. value	Max. value	Means(μ)	SDs (σ)
Tube 1	K	2.9	4.5	3.63	0.33
Tube 2	K	3.3	4.4	3.76	0.14
Tube 3	K	3.4	5	4.2	0.24
Tube 4	K	3	4.8	3.66	0.36

The CUSUM chart works by accumulating deviations from observations that are above a target value μ_0 with one statistic C^+ , and accumulating deviations from observations that are below the target value μ_0 with another statistic C^- . The statistics C^+ and C^- are called one-sided upper and lower CUSUM, respectively and have the following form:

$$C_i^+ = \max[0, X_i - (\mu_0 + K) + C_{i-1}^+] \quad (2)$$

$$C_i^- = \max[0, (\mu_0 - K) - X_i + C_{i-1}^-] \quad (3)$$

where the starting values $C_0^+ = C_0^- = 0$.

These charts depend on the definition of the ARL0, which is the minimum number of samples needed to reduce the probability that the control chart indicates biofilm when biofilm is not present (false positive, type I error) or indicates no biofilm, when biofilm is present (false negative, type II error) (Montgomery et al. 2009). The average value of the ARL0 samples is called μ_0 . In a previous study (Boullosa-Falces et al. 2019), an ARL0 value of 375 was established for this type of heat exchanger.

The value K , called the allowance when the cumulative deviations is considered to be significant and determines the sensitivity of the control chart. This value is selected according to the SD (σ_0) and is determined following the form:

$$K = k \delta \sigma_0 \quad (4)$$

where k is a tabulated value, frequently selected to be 0.5, which was validated for this type of heat exchanger (Boullosa-Falces et al. 2019); δ represents the change in the mean in units of SD that are to be detected, with a value of 3 for this type of heat exchanger (Boullosa-Falces et al. 2019); and σ_0 is the SD of the process targeted for the control.

Finally, the decision interval H , established the limit at which the control needs to be implemented, rather, the values C_i^+ and C_i^- , must be compared with the control limits of the chart and defined by the decision interval H , and was determined by the following equation:

$$H = h \delta \sigma_0 \quad (5)$$

where h is a tabulated value, based on the average run length (ARL0) and k , the relevant tables for which can be found in the literature (Hawkins and Olwell 2012); σ_0 is the SD of the process targeted for the control. When the value of C_i^+ or C_i^- exceeds the value of H , the process is considered to be out of control.

Heat duty

The capacity of a heat exchanger is represented by the rate at which it transfers heat between streams, known as the heat duty and expressed in terms of heat transfer per unit time. The heat duty can be determined from the heat gained by the cooling fluid, which is equal to the heat lost from the hot fluid. The heat duty of an exchanger with clean tubes, in its initial condition, can be expressed as:

$$q_{No\ biofilm} = \dot{m}_c \cdot Cp_c \cdot (T_{c,o} - T_{c,i}) \quad (6)$$

The heat transfer with EMF treatment can be expressed as:

$$q_{EMF} = \dot{m}_c \cdot Cp_c \cdot (T_{c,o} - T_{c,i}) \quad (7)$$

The heat transfer without treatment can be expressed as:

$$q_{No\ treated} = \dot{m}_c \cdot Cp_c \cdot (T_{c,o} - T_{c,i}) \quad (8)$$

Biofilm characterization

Biofilm adhered to the internal surface of the tubes in the heat exchanger was determined through the thickness and composition of the biofilm, which depended on the solid matter deposited on the internal surface tubes with weights and dimensions measured. The biofilm thickness was calculated (Trueba, Vega et al. 2015):

$$e = \frac{\Delta m}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot r \cdot l \cdot \partial} \cdot 10^4 \quad (9)$$

Biofilm composition was determined as the difference between the weight of wet and dry biofilm. The biofilm samples were dried at 105 °C for 4 h. Then the organic and inorganic matter were determined as the difference between the weight of the dry biofilm and the biofilm incinerated at 550 °C for 12 h, and the remainder was inorganic matter (Trueba, Vega et al. 2015).

Biofilm thermal conductivity is the quantity of heat transmitted through a unit thickness of biofilm in a direction normal to a surface of unit area due to a temperature gradient under steady state conditions, and it was determined based on the heat transfer resistance and the thickness of the biofilm at the end of experiment, in accordance with Equation (10) (López-Galindo et al. 2010):

$$\lambda_{biofilm} = \frac{e}{\Delta R_f} \quad (10)$$

Uncertainty measurements

The system error and uncertainties cannot be avoided in the instruments and procedure for making measurements. For the system device errors, an uncertainty analysis was conducted based on the accuracy of the instrument used to perform the measurement. The relative uncertainty of indirect measured value can be calculated by Equation (11) (Boullosa-Falces et al. 2019):

$$W_R^+ = \left(\left(\frac{\delta R^+}{\delta X_1} w_1 \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\delta R^+}{\delta X_2} w_2 \right)^2 + \dots + \left(\frac{\delta R^+}{\delta X_n} w_n \right)^2 \right)^{1/2} \quad (11)$$

Experimental plan

Experiments were conducted to evaluate the efficiency and economic viability of the EMF AF treatment and the proposed CUSUM control method. In the pilot plant shown in Figure 1, continuous EMF treatment was applied to

Tubes 2 and 3 of the heat exchanger. Tubes 1 and 4 were not treated and served as controls for comparison. The results were expressed as the mean values of the measurements of the two tubes in each experimental group.

The data acquisition system of the pilot plant consisted of four configurable multifunction modules (STEP model DL01-CPU, STEP Logistics and Control, Barcelona, Spain) that controlled and recorded the parameters of the plant in real time. These data were managed by software (TCS-01 version 3.0.3) and stored on a computer.

Before performing the experiment, a thorough cleaning of the heat exchanger was carried out. The data acquisition was carried out during the months of July and September, which is the period of the year in which the maximum biological activity occurs (Eguía and Trueba 2007). During this period, the average room temperature was 21 °C, and the hydraulic conditions in each of the four tubes were maintained at a constant flow velocity of 1 m s⁻¹ and a constant flow rate of 4.8 l min⁻¹. A total of 1,464 samples were acquired at 1-h intervals, over the full 60 days that the experiment lasted, and 100% of the acquired samples were analysed.

Results

Evolution of biofilm growth

As shown in Figure 3, the progression of the heat transfer resistance, R_f , was different in the two experimental groups (control and treated) and showed three clearly differentiated growth phases: induction, exponential growth, and levelling off (Trueba et al. 2014; García et al. 2016). The R_f values showed that the exponential growth phase occurred from Days 10 to 45 in the control tubes (Tubes 1 and 4) and from Days 10 to 40 in the treated tubes (Tubes 2 and 3). Thereafter, in the levelling off phase, the R_f increases were small until Day 60. In the control tubes, R_f showed increases of 28% and 29% with respect to the initial values (Day 0). In the treated tubes, R_f increased by 11% and 13% with respect to the initial values.

Figure 3. Progression in heat transfer resistance (R_f) during the experimental phase.

The R_f evolution was linear in the control tubes, with an average increase over the initial value of 28%. In contrast, the R_f evolution in the treated tubes showed an average reduction of 35% compared to the control tubes. This reduction was caused by a combination of effects caused by the EMF treatment of the seawater: (1) a decreased surface roughness with less biofilm, which reduced the convective heat transfer resistance, and (2) a lower concentration of dissolved solids in the biofilm that reduced the conductive heat transfer.

Evaluation of EMF treatment performance by the CUSUM chart

The performance of the EMF treatment in all tubes was monitored using the CUSUM charts, based on Equations (1) and (2). The first 375 samples established the ARL0 (Boullosa-Falces et al. 2019), and the next 1089 samples were monitored and controlled. The means and SD of the ΔT in the ARL0, control, and treated samples are presented in Table 2. Figures 4 through 7 present the CUSUM control charts for Tubes 1 through 4, respectively. If any value

was below the control limit H , the control chart indicated that the process was out of control, that is, the temperature difference was lower than that established in the ARL0 group, indicating that the tube interior had become fouled and was not operating optimally. Table 3 summarizes the results obtained from the control charts.

Table 2. Standard deviations and means of new samples and ARL0 (Tubes 1–4).

		ΔT (K)	
		Means (μ)	SDs (σ)
Tube 1	ARL0	4.04	0.14
	New samples	3.43	0.55
Tube 2	ARL0	3.84	0.16
	New samples	3.67	0.55
Tube 3	ARL0	4.43	0.20
	New samples	4.04	0.61
Tube 4	ARL0	4.15	0.21
	New samples	3.43	0.54

Table 3. Results of CUSUM control chart.

	Tube 1	Tube 2	Tube 3	Tube 4
H	-1.75	-1.94	-2.49	-2.63
K	0.21	0.23	0.30	0.32
μ_0	4.04	3.84	4.43	4.15
ARL0	375	375	375	375
Minimum number of samples to record a change in the process	30	490	470	83
Number of monitored samples before signalling	405	865	845	458
Detection day since last cleaning	17	36	35	19

Heat transfer efficiency

These data showed that the EMF treatment significantly mitigated the biofilm. Figure 8 illustrates the fall off in heat duty with and without EMF treatment. The trends were almost identical in the control and treated groups until 15 days after the start of the experiment. After Day 16, the heat transfer efficiency in the control tubes diminished more than in the treated tubes. At the end of the experiment, the control tubes showed a 22% reduction in heat duty, whereas the treated tubes showed only a 9% reduction in heat duty compared with the initial values.

Quantitative determination of biofilm adhered inside the tube surfaces

The measurements taken in the untreated control tubes at the end of the experiment showed a mean biofilm thickness of 429 μm . The mean biofilm was composed of 78% water, 13% inorganic matter and 9% organic matter (Figure 9). The mean concentration of dissolved solids was 9.7 mg cm^{-2} where 61% was inorganic matter and 39% was organic matter. The measurements taken in the treated tubes with EMFs at the end of the experiment showed a biofilm thickness of 246 μm . The quantitative analysis of biofilm showed to up 92% water, 5% inorganic matter and 3% organic matter (Figure 9). The mean concentration of dissolved solids was 1.9 mg cm^{-2} , which 69% was inorganic matter and 31% was organic matter. The mean biofilm thermal conductivity of biofilm in control tubes was of 1.44 W

$m^{-1} K^{-1}$ at the end of experiment. On other hand, biofilm in EMF treatment tubes showed a thermal conductivity of $2.59 W m^{-1} K^{-1}$.

Uncertainty measurements

Because the measured biofilm resistances were small, the uncertainty analysis was especially critical. The uncertainty attributed to experimental parameters showed minimal deviations (Table 4), supporting the validity and reliability of the results. The R_f mean error was 4.3%, resulting from errors in the measurement of the heat transfer area, the heat transfer rate, and the mean temperature difference. The heat duty deviation was 5.6%, resulting from fluctuations in the volumetric flow rates, the hydraulic diameter, and the flow temperatures during the experimental period.

Table 4. Maximum uncertainty of parameters.

Parameter	Unit	Bias uncertainty
Hot water inlet temperature	K	± 0.15
Hot seawater outlet temperature	K	± 0.15
Cold seawater inlet temperature	K	± 0.15
Cold water outlet temperature	K	± 0.15
Diameter of tubes	mm	± 0.01
Hot water flow rate	$m^3 h^{-1}$	± 0.07
Cold seawater flow rate	$m^3 h^{-1}$	± 0.1
Heat transfer resistance	%	± 4.3
Heat duty	%	± 5.6
Uncertainty in reading values from table (e.g. C_p , ρ)	%	± 0.3

Discussion

The heat exchanger in the experimental pilot plant cooled by seawater created ideal conditions for the initiation of biofilm inside the tubes. The R_f in turbulent flow is the sum of conduction and convection thermal resistances. Convective heat transfer resistance results from heat transport caused by the motion and mixing of macroscopic portions of a fluid (García et al. 2016), and its value depends on the effect of biofilm on the boundary layer of the fluid and on the turbulence at the interface between the fluid and the tube. Conductive heat transfer resistance is the result of heat transport from a high-temperature liquid to a low-temperature liquid. According to previous reports (Trueba et al. 2014; García et al. 2016), R_f values decrease during the initial days of these types of experiments (as shown in Figure 3) because of changes in the roughness of the internal tube surface that favour heat transfer by convection due to the generation of turbulent eddies in the boundary layer. When biofilm deposits refill rough cavities in the tube, the flow turbulence decreases and the insulating biofilm increases, thereby increasing R_f values.

In this study, the trends in the R_f values of untreated and treated tubes did not diverge until the exponential growth phase. According to previous studies (Gabrielli et al. 2001; Xiaokai 2008), certain conditions are required for biofilm deposition, such as crystal nucleation and surface conditioning, and these conditions were established in the untreated tubes in this study during the induction phase. In contrast, these deposition conditions were not established in the treated tubes because the EMF treatment induced the precipitation of dissolved ions that crystallized into particles that then became suspended in the flow current (Trueba et al. 2015b). These circumstances inhibited biofilm adhesion and induced a lower concentration of solids dissolved in the biofilm, which reduced the conductive heat transfer in the exponential growth phase (Trueba et al. 2015b). Therefore, the R_f values of the treated tubes progressively diminished until they stabilized in the levelling off phase. Thus, the R_f values of the treated tubes were lower than those of the untreated tubes at the end of the experiment.

The R_f of a tubular heat exchanger depends on the temperature and the velocity of the cooling seawater (Li et al. 2016). In the absence of flow changes, it is possible to evaluate the performance of the AF treatment in a heat ex-

changer by analysing the temperature gradients between the inlet and effluent *via* the CUSUM method, as was previously demonstrated (Boullosa-Falces et al. 2019). Figures 4 and 7 present the evolution of biofilm growth in the control tubes (Tubes 1 and 4, respectively), where the lack of treatment allowed the free adherence of the biofilm on the tube walls. Figures 5 and 6 present the evolution of biofilm growth in Tubes 2 and 3, in which continuous EMF treatment hindered the biological growth on the tube walls.

Figure 4. CUSUM chart (Tube 1).

Figure 5. CUSUM chart (Tube 2).

Figure 6. CUSUM chart (Tube 3).

Figure 7. CUSUM chart (Tube 4).

In Tube 1, a progressive decrease in the C-statistic was observed from Sample 8, exceeding the control limit H in Sample 30. For the corresponding samples from Tube 2, the C-statistic acquired values close to the target value μ_0 for a longer time and tended to take null values up to Sample 465, at which point a progressive decrease in the C-statistic began, indicating that biofilm had adhered to the surface of the tube. This caused a slow decrease in the temperature difference, until the control limit was exceeded in Sample 490, indicating that from Day 36 (865 h from the start of the experiment), the heat exchanger did not operate under optimal conditions.

In Tube 3, the CUSUM statistic remained constant at close to zero until Sample 442, and during this period of time, the heat transfer was maximized. After Sample 442, the EMF treatment ceased to be effective and the biofilm growth on the tube walls produced a slow and progressive decrease in heat exchange capability until Sample 470, indicating that from Day 35 (845 h since the last cleaning), the heat transfer was lower than it would have been under optimal operating conditions. In contrast, in Tube 4, the heat transfer was maximized only for the first 16 days (395 h from the beginning), and from Day 16, the heat transfer progressively decreased until Day 19 (458 h from the beginning), at which point the control limit was exceeded, indicating that the heat exchanger was not working under optimal conditions at a much earlier point in the untreated tube.

The EMF treatment was therefore considered to increase the useful life of the heat exchanger by ~ 20 days. This translates into an increase in the time between necessary cleaning and maintenance events and a decrease in operation and maintenance costs. Although the EMF treatment is effective at weakening the biofilm and lengthening the useful life of the exchanger, the treatment nonetheless reaches a point where it stops being efficient. To enhance its effectiveness, EMF treatment should be combined with other physical treatments, either from the beginning of operation or when the EMF treatment ceases to be effective.

The heat duty values improved during the initial days of the experiment (Figure 8) because of small changes in the roughness of the tube surface that favoured heat duty by convection by amplifying the turbulent boundary layer (Trueba et al. 2013). After biofilm deposits refilled the tube cavities, the flow turbulence decreased, and the insulating biofilm increased, reducing the heat duty.

Figure 8. Reduction in heat duty in untreated (1 and 4) and EMF-treated (2 and 3) tubes.

Figure 9. Mean thickness and composition of the biofouling at the end of the experiment.

As reported by previous authors (Melo and Pinheiro 1992; Müller-Steinhagen et al. 2011; Garcia et al. 2017), a loss of heat duty and the subsequent decrease in the outlet temperature results from the low thermal conductivity of the biofilm layer. Because of this, the heat duty was decreased and the effectiveness and thermal efficiency of the tubes were reduced. EMF treatment has been reported to show positive AF properties that reduce heat duty loss from the tube surfaces of a heat exchanger because of the effect of the treatment on the crystallization and deposition rate of calcium carbonate. The results of the proposed CUSUM method indicate that heat duty loss can be reduced through EMF treatment.

The mean biofilm thickness was up to 30% less in the EMF treatment tubes than in the control tubes. The presence of organic and inorganic matter was up to 84% and 77% less, respectively. These findings are due to the reduction in divalent cations which damage the electrostatic interaction between carboxylate functional groups on the polysaccharide and the divalent cations, thereby the bridging effect between the polymer chains was affected (Ly et al. 2019). Therefore, EMF treatment still reduced by 80% the total solids at the biofilm surface due to divalent cations which did not fix into the matrix to affect a bridging effect between the polymer chains, thereby weakening the growing biofilm matrix and reducing the adhesion capacity. Biofilm structure can be compared as a coating of microbial cells and biopolymer that is spread evenly across a surface. Biofilm adhesion with EMF treatment was reduced and the heat transfer efficiency was increased. In accordance with Trueba et al. (2015b), Figure 10 demonstrates that thermal

conductivity was increased by EMF treatment compared with the control tubes. The CUSUM method detected these small changes during continuous monitoring of the heat exchanger while applying EMF treatment.

Figure 10. Mean solids and thermal conductivity of the biofouling at the end of the experiment.

The initial cost of EMF equipment is low compared with the maintenance costs, renewal of the devices affected, loss of production and problems of corrosion induced by biofouling. On the other hand, the increase in CaCO₃ precipitated by EMF treatment has no significant effect on the environment and is environmentally innocuous.

The algorithm was developed so that its implementation is simple and economical, through only the analysis of the temperature difference between the inlet and outlet of the cooling water. The inlet and outlet temperatures can be acquired with conventional equipment and are supported by the basic instrumentation of any type of heat exchanger. However, other variables such as Rf are more difficult to acquire. On the other hand, conventional methods of monitoring biofilm are more complex and need to develop new algorithms based on the variation in the physical-chemical conditions of the water. The Cusum method does not depend on the physical-chemical conditions of the water, such as pH or conductivity, so, once the algorithm has been developed for a type of heat exchanger and treatment, it is possible to apply it in any marine environment for this type of heat exchanger.

As mentioned above, the Cusum is a predictive method, so maintenance managers could establish preventive protocols before the heat exchanger operates below optimal operating conditions thus avoiding energy and production losses or unplanned shutdowns.

Conclusions

This study investigated the effects of biofilm on the efficiency of heat exchangers with and without EMF treatment. The results showed that the EMF treatment could reduce interruptions to production necessitated by maintenance requirements, and would thereby contribute to increased profits. A CUSUM-based surveillance system was also proposed and was shown to be effective at continuous monitoring of AF treatments using the data collected online. This tool could allow industries to improve energy efficiency and reduce production losses caused by unplanned shutdowns and maintenance costs due to fouling.

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Declaration of interests

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Nomenclature

A	surface of tube wall, m ²
AF	antifouling

ARLO	Average run length
C	deviation
CUSUM	Cumulative Cusum Charts
C _p	specific heat at constant pressure, J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
d	diameter, m
EMF	electromagnetic field
H	Control limit of CUSUM Charts
h	Tabulated value from ARLO and k
K	Reference value which the cumulative deviation is considered to be significant
k	Tabulated value, typically value of 0.5
L	tube length, m
\dot{m}	water mass flow rate, kg s ⁻¹
l	test tube length, cm
P	power device, W
q	heat transfer rate, W
r	test tube internal radius, cm
R	overall uncertainty in the result
R _f	heat transfer resistance without treatment, m ² K W ⁻¹
T	fluid temperature, K
v	velocity flow, m s ⁻¹
w	independent uncertainty in the measurement
W	total uncertainty in the measurement
X	independent variable

Greek symbols

ρ	density, kg m ⁻³
σ_0	standard deviation
μ_0	objective value

Subscripts

c	cold
h	hot
i	inlet
o	outlet

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